

Time Management in Professional Business Life

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Pamir DİRİL¹

Naz DEĞİRMENCI²

To cite this article: Collaborate, Current Science, Volume 6, No. 6-5, 2025, p. 52–85. - 0099-0001-2505-04916.

Our studies are in a format accredited, approved, and supported by EAALS - European Academic Studies and Laboratory Services. (“Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia”) “EAALS offers all our works, services, and publications to the world scientists at the stage of carrying our control, accreditation, and support processes to the international platform.” (“CURRENT SCIENCE”)

(“Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia”) ISSN: 2667-9515

¹ St. Clements University , Psychology Department Faculty Member , Orcid ID: 0000-0001-8913-343X, Mail: akademisyen1970@hotmail.com

² St. Clements University , Business Management PhD Department , Orcid ID: ,

Mail naz_degirmenci@hotmail.com

Barcode:

977266795001

Editors Group:

Concessionaire: Tsisana Kharabadze

Niyaz Bokvadze

Prof. Sabrina Corbi

Prof. Samantha
Lewes

““Current Science Multidisciplinary Academic Journal with

Review Panel is a monthly multidisciplinary academic” (“CURRENT SCIENCE (“Scientific
Studies – Current Science Georgia”) (“Scientific Studies - Current

Science Georgia”) Science Georgia”) journal with a multi-science peer-review.” (“Scientific
Studies - Current Science Georgia”)

““The journal will be at the subscriber's address in the first week of the month.” (“Scientific
Studies - Current Science Georgia”)

- The journal continues to be included in all international rankings and

registrations. Quality articles and publications accelerate this (“Scientific Studies

-Current Science Georgia”)

““Response or rejection time for applications varies between 30 and 90 days.””

(“Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia”)

Abstract

Time is equal for everyone, but how it is used varies from person to person. Most people complain that their work is not completed in one day, whereas people who are successful in time management even find time to spare time for themselves. Time management is to determine how to plan the work in a certain time frame. At this stage, training plays a big role. Trainings support more effective and efficient use of time management. The aim of this study is to analyze time well and how it should be managed and the time traps we will be confused with have been investigated.

Keywords: Time, time management, time traps, planning, education

Introduction

When we say time management, the first things that come to mind are situations such as planning and scheduling, but they constitute only one point of time management and are incomplete in explaining this concept. Time management is basically divided into personal and organizational time management, and although these two concepts are very similar, they are different in terms of the application of time management elements to personal or managerial actions. The similar points are to combine all managerial or personal actions on a basis with a certain perspective in order to harmonize them with time. But even if time management is conceptually separated in this way, it is not possible to separate personal life and work life. Because from a broad perspective, it can be interpreted that time management equals life management. Time is a resource in both personal and business life,

and when used correctly, competitiveness and productivity emerge. The concept of "time management" has emerged, which indicates the practices related to the concept of time. In this study, the concepts of time and time management are examined from a broad perspective and their relationship with various concepts, both personal and managerial, is examined.

Purpose and Scope of the Study

To examine the concepts of time and time management from a broad perspective is to try to solve how the issue should be perceived in terms of businesses and employees. After examining the concept of time and time management from as broad a perspective as possible, time management practices themselves are covered. In this study, the researches that form the cornerstones of the time management literature and give direction have been mentioned as much as possible. In a broad perspective, the concept of time management has been examined and its relations and mutual effects with other concepts have been mentioned.

Time Description

Among all explanations, time is one of the most difficult phenomena to define. Although scientists have made different definitions from different perspectives, studies are still ongoing in various branches of science to explain it. It is very difficult to define because of its lack of dimension, width and depth: "Time consists of past, present and future and is not a concept under the control of individuals." (H. Smith, 1998: p. 19) If time exists, objectivity exists. The speed of time is related to the speed of the person.

Time is a very important concept that is equal for everyone. Time is not a resource that can be accumulated and stopped. One resource can be replaced by another, for example, manpower can be replaced by machinery. However, we cannot replace time in any way "Human life is full of multifaceted and varied actions. The value of action is often measured

in time." (Sabuncuoğlu, 2010: p. 3-4) Going to work on time, the end of the shift, the start time of work are related to time. Time is a concept that can be measured. Past, present and future are considered as a whole. It is a synonym of the word "time" and has entered our language from the Arabic word "zeman". Time should be planned, directed and kept under control in order to use it effectively.

Time Perception and Time Types

It is the realization that time has passed. It can be explained by the change in the space they occupy in time and the time between them. Time perception always covers the time experienced; one cannot perceive the time of events that have happened or will happen. The time interval between the events experienced constitutes the perception of time. " In everyday life, many things are done and a certain amount of time passes between them, and time is perceived during this transition." (Tutar, 2007; p.23-25) Although it is not possible to experience someone else's perception of time, it can be objectively examined." Differences in the perception of time are indisputably linked to social development." (Elias, 2000, p. 180) Because time is subjective and perceived differently from person to person.

Time Types

Since time passes quickly in some cases and slowly in others, it is divided into objective (real) and subjective (perceived) time. Objective time is time that can be measured. Subjective time is the time we perceive, which is not easy to measure. It is not about the clock, it is about the perception of time

Objective time is the time that we base on the clock and that can be measured. It is measured by a clock. It occurs as a result of the Earth's movement around the Sun. Objective time occurs equally for all people. It refers to the time that needs to be managed within the scope of time management.

CURRENT SCIENCE

Subjective time is the time we feel. It is also referred to as psychological time. The industry and minutes, which are the same for all of us, can be perceived differently. Sometimes we do not realize how time passes, it may pass faster or slower than we think; because time management is also thought to have a psychology. For example, when we are having a great and fun time, time passes very fast, whereas for a man waiting for his wife in labor, he may think that even minutes pass very slowly. The way we define ourselves is based on past experiences, our memories. These time-space experiences make a person unique in the world. Everyone has a unique perception of time. For example, although time is made up of measurable phenomena based on a clock, everyone has different ideas about time. Some people feel like they have "all the time in the world", while others feel like they don't even have "enough time". This reflects people's personality and way of thinking.

Time Management Concept

The problem in time management is not time but how people use their time and what they do with it. These techniques can be listed as follows: planning, goal setting, time analysis, observation and prioritization. Time management means the efficient use of a limited resource. In order to use time efficiently, it is necessary to identify important points. Because the efficient use of time means not only achieving successful results in business life, but also being successful in people's lives outside of work.

The aim of time management is to do the right things in a short time. "Managers who use their time inefficiently are overwhelmed and cannot develop their skills due to reasons such as not being able to complete their work in the specified time periods, overlapping urgent work, etc." (Sabuncuoğlu-Paşa-Kaymaz, 2010; p.6-9) The first rule in time management is to create a to-do list after planning the day. The important thing is to establish a healthy work-life balance. The main goal is not to work hard but to work effectively.

Different Approaches

Regular Life Approach

This approach arises from the unestablished order in life. It is the planning and sequencing of the work one needs to do. Creating an order saves time and increases productivity. It is divided into 3. Organizing objects; organizing files, documents, in short, organizing the objects around us. Organizing tasks; preparing a to-do list. Organizing people; it can be stated as delegating tasks to be done, monitoring people. Strengths; It saves time, increases efficiency and creates organization. People spend the productive part of time planning instead of producing. Although the employee is doing his/her work because he/she is busy with plans, he/she is actually postponing his/her work. A time management that deals with fine details is far from comfort turns the person into a time machine.

Warrior

It is the protection of time. Protecting the time allocated for themselves. People can be in a busy work environment. The warrior approach is about protecting one's own time despite time traps. If managers allocate their precious time to unimportant tasks, they will not have time for the important work that needs to be done. Because urgent work is the most important. The most important reason for difficulty in starting work is the desire to "eliminate unimportant issues first and then start working". Here, it is important to plan the work according to the order of importance, rather than dividing it into important and unimportant tasks." The warrior approach is the approach of eliminating traps. The person who fights against time tries to eliminate the traps." (Tutar, 2007; p.64) Thus, the person focuses on the time allocated to him/herself;

1. Isolating oneself; having closed doors and no contact when working.
2. Being alone; choosing a place to be alone so as not to be disturbed.
3. Delegating authority; giving tasks to other employees so that I can do important work.

CURRENT SCIENCE

Strengths; when time is productive and free from unsettling situations, it is creative. It takes responsibility for the time. It uses this approach when the employee is productive.
Weaknesses; sees employees as enemies. It is a struggle for survival.

ABC

It is based on the idea of ranking priorities. The main idea of the ABC approach is: focus on your most important tasks. A stands for most important tasks, B for moderately important tasks and C for less important tasks. The ABC Approach is inspired by the "Goal Setting Approach". The goal is this: "If you focus your efforts on prioritized tasks, you will be successful in that task." Strengths: The ABC Approach is a "prioritization of important tasks" approach. It aims to understand the difference between to-do tasks and priority tasks.
Weaknesses; They set goals and made extraordinary efforts to achieve them. But when they achieved what they wanted, they realized that it did not bring the results they expected. Valuing something and achieving it may not bring lasting happiness. Basically, if the values are not right, we will never be satisfied.

Magic Tool Approach

It follows the rule that "good things are done with good tools". The approach is based on the power of the right technological tool to improve quality of life. An organizer, a phone or a computer are essential for planning daily tasks. In the magic tool approach, the concept of time is considered to be magical. They are helpful for observing and planning tasks.
Strengths: the right tools make things happen more efficiently. Developments in technological tools have been realized just to do things effectively in a shorter time.
Weaknesses: Good tools are not enough for the "right things". Vision, mission and the right decision are necessary. The most perfect tool cannot replace elements such as innovation and character.

Skill Approach

" The skill approach is based on the idea that time management is basically a skill, like accounting or word processing." (Sabuncuoğlu-Paşa-Kaymaz, 2010; p.38-39) Managers who do not plan often face crises. If planning is done regularly, crises can be overcome with little damage. Small plans can save the manager from wasted minutes. It is necessary to develop skills such as using an agenda, creating to-do lists and setting goals. Strengths; To be successful, it is necessary to work effectively instead of working hard. This is possible with knowledge and skills. Weaknesses; Nowadays, most of the time management training content consists of topics such as saving time and planning. Skills alone are not enough.

Goal Setting Approach

"It refers to the effort we make to set a goal and to achieve the goal we set." (Doğruöz, 2008; p. 5) Success is an important key to achieving the goal. Realizing this is possible through time management. It deals with issues such as plans, goals and setting priorities. Goal setting approach is an effective method to increase performance by motivating people.

Rehabilitation Approach

The improvement approach is considered to be based on social, cultural or psychological reasons. The solution is to improve the cultural and psychological factors that greatly influence time management. As emphasized earlier, the way people perceive time is not the same. Some people see it as a "value to be studied in depth", while others see it as a "value to be lived".

Going with the Flow Approach

" The essence of this approach is to learn to go with the flow and be open to life and unexpected events" (Tutar, 2007; p. 70). It emerged as a reaction to the person who does his/her job fast and in a hurry. Here, on the contrary, the aim is not to manage time but to adapt to the flow of time.

Stress, Performance and Time Management

If we want to use time efficiently, we need to move away from tension. With tense time, the desired result can be achieved, but it is much more difficult than the alternative of staying calm and doing the job. Jex and Elacqua's (1999) work-related stress research has shown that a stressful work environment negatively affects mental and physical health. These effects lead to poorer performance and often a lower quality of life for the employee. Those who study work stress look for ways to reduce the effects of work-related stressors. These arrangements include occupational health programs and training. "A much simpler and less costly way to eliminate stressors is to use "time management behaviors." (Jex and Elacqua, 1999; p. 182)

Planning and Time Management

A plan is a form of action that specifies what work needs to be done and when it needs to be done in order for the business to achieve its goals. All businesses, whether global or small firms, should engage in planning activities. With effective planning, organizations can foresee and use their resources in the most accurate way. "Planning is a matter of basic choice and is valid in the case of different choices and decisions." (Sabuncuoğlu-Paşa-Kaymaz, 2010; p.11) The biggest advantage of planning is that it saves time for employees. When the employee knows what he/she is doing, he/she controls his/her time.

The success of each work is determined by the criteria that determine how the employee will achieve his or her goals within the agreed time frame. A plan is the result of decisions and indicates certain situations to be achieved. Thus, a plan can be expressed as "deciding

now on the goals to be implemented in the future". Therefore, making decisions and making plans mean the same thing in a sense. The difference is that plans involve more than one decision, while decisions are the sum of them. Planning is all of the intellectual processes to achieve a goal or objective. Here, the necessary steps are planned, visualized, resources are put forward and necessary controls are made. Past experiences and data are utilized in this process.

If a person is the present instead of looking to the future, he/she will not think about basic planning questions. "If we focus on the manager; managers are a "trustee" to whom material and manpower resources are transferred in order to implement their goals." (Koçel, 2007; p.93-94) At this point, it is seen that the concepts of planning and time management overlap. Although both are oriented towards the future, the same things can be said since they will work with a continuous action. In the light of this point of view, if we make a distinction in order to avoid concept confusion, time management refers to doing business for the future based on planning. Time management also includes psychological concepts. Although forecasting and planning seem to be very close in meaning, they are different. "Forecasting" is about trying to find alternatives to situations. "Planning" is about determining what to do to improve things. Forecasting is defined as making predictions about the future based on intuition.

Decision Making

It refers to "making a choice between alternatives" or in other words "mental efforts to make a choice among various options". If the relationship between time and decision-making is examined, the goal to be achieved should be a goal that can be predicted, predicted, realized in the shortest time and maximizes the profitability of organizations. The manager should be able to access all data to achieve this goal and make effective decisions in terms of competition with businesses. Appropriate decisions in terms of time make organizations successful. Wrong decisions, on the other hand, cause losses. Managers should keep the time that can be realized at the optimum level when making decisions. In

the decision-making process, management should have the ability to monitor the results. Even if there is a deviation from the desired goal, it should be corrected immediately. The time element in the decision-making process is the most important condition to ensure competition.

Organization and Time Management

The term organization is divided into two. The first is organization, which means a skeleton. The second refers to the actions of creating the organization. "In the simplest terms, the reason for the existence of an organization is that certain objectives can only be achieved with more than one person and as a group." (Koçel, 2007; p.20-21) In businesses, planning refers to the work applied to achieve the goals as soon as possible. One of the important duties of top management is to establish an effective organization and ensure its continuity. Unless the organizational structure of an enterprise is based on realities, even the business policies created at the management level become unworkable. Managers need to know what work they need to do, who will help them and to whom they will be responsible for the work done. This situation means organization.

Delegation of Authority

In the context of delegation, authority is based on one employee telling and directing another employee to do something. Authority also includes the use of any resources, people, etc., to accomplish a task. It is through authority that jobs and tasks are performed and controlled. Authority keeps the business afloat. It is the top management's request to employees to do the current work in order to achieve its goals. Authority covers decision-making and commanding situations. Delegation of authority is the authorization of other people to perform existing tasks. But usually managers do not want to give authority to others. Because they think that it requires too much time and effort and that they will do

the job better. Effective delegation of authority to other employees is very important in terms of mobilizing employees.

Audit

Ensuring controls on whether predetermined targets have been achieved. It seeks answers to the questions of whether and to what extent the objectives have been achieved. Audit is to compare the results of the actual situation with the standards and create a new stage. One of these standards is time. To create a time audit, we can start by making a list of what we spend time on during the day. This gives us clues about which areas we can make more efficient.

Time Management Training

It is a training given to enable people to use their time more effectively, efficiently and productively. It helps people to be more efficient in their work and private life, to do their work quickly and effectively, and to control stress and pressure. These trainings are carried out through group work, slides, presentations and practical applications. Today, training activities implemented in enterprises are important in terms of supporting the structural change of enterprises, reducing costs, reducing error rates and adapting to changing technology. The knowledge and skills developed as a result of training activities also improve the problem solving skills of employees

" The training on "time planning techniques", which many managers in companies have received, guides managers to use time more effectively in their work and social life. "Teamwork" trainings are important for managers to improve the work efficiency of the employees they work with. Receiving training on teamwork and providing this information to subordinates will help managers to reduce their workload and save time. Again, "problem solving skills" trainings will provide managers with the ability to quickly solve the problems they encounter in their work and will be beneficial in time management. This

naturally reduces the time allocated to problems. "Trainings on motivation affect people positively; since highly motivated employees are more confident, more creative and have the lowest margin of error, they save time by reducing the supervision time of senior management." (Sabuncuoğlu-Paşa-Kaymaz, 2010; p.25-27)

Time Traps

Situations that prevent the effective use of time are called time traps. These are traps arising from work, traps arising from people, traps arising from businesses and management

Personal Time Traps

Lack of Self-Discipline

Self-discipline is the ability to choose behavior from within oneself, without the control of an external authority. It is acquired with age and experience. Unless children gain self-discipline, they will need the help of adults. Self-disciplined people are better at managing time because they are not under the control of one person. They don't feel constantly under the pressure of time." Managers should examine their habits that prevent the efficient use of time management and consider what routines should be done to them." (İşcan, 1999; pp. 86-87)

Uncertainty of Individual Goals

Goals drive people to new behaviors. Without effort, employees cannot maintain their current situation. Moving beyond the status quo and moving forward is a matter of setting goals and objectives and working. " Since the set goals have a time scale, if the goals make work and life meaningful, they motivate the person." (Tutar, 2007; pp. 81-82)

Procrastination and Stalling

Leaving a task to be done for a later time. In this way, the work to be done in the future is also postponed and this situation continues in a chain. Postponing work is postponing life. The saying "don't leave today's work for tomorrow" should be "don't leave tomorrow's work for tomorrow". Because tomorrow is uncertain. Therefore, if possible, by doing tomorrow's work today, the opportunity to make time for a sudden development that may occur tomorrow can be created.

Not Being Able to Say No

It is an effective time management behavior to take a firm stand on work that is not a priority. This does not mean rejecting people all the time. It is simply stating to the other person, for valid reasons, what the situation is that needs to be focused on at that moment. When we cannot say no, time is used inefficiently as we try to please the other person. When we meet every external demand, we delay our work. To be successful in the time method, we must be able to say no and be in control of the time.

Indecision

People who have difficulty in making decisions have difficulty in time management. A person who cannot decide which work to prioritize and what the important work is cannot get efficiency from time. He/she has difficulty in planning the work. Due to indecision, the direction to be taken in line with the manager's choices will not be clear, so losses will occur.

Perfectionism

CURRENT SCIENCE

Perfectionism can be found in many people. Since these people are obsessed with too much detail, they take time to complete tasks that could be completed immediately. At the same time, since the employee thinks that only he/she will do the job well, he/she has difficulty in managing time with too much workload.

Open Door Policy

Considering the continuity of communication, employees who see the door open and walk in and chat, even to say hello, affect concentration and waste time. As a solution, it may be advisable to close the door or sit with the back facing the door.

Uncertainty of Priorities

This section should be kept separate from the section on the uncertainty of individual goals. This is because a person may have individual goals but some problems arise when he/she does not prioritize his/her daily actions. To solve this time-related problem, a daily to-do list can be created.

Stress and Time Pressure

" Stress activates the cycle to adapt to the unique biochemical conditions in one's body." (Emmet, 2009; p.19) Stress is a fact of life. Zero stress is like death. Because the individual has no energy to react to the effects of the environment. The solution is to continue one's life with the stress that one can endure.

Work-related Time Traps

CURRENT SCIENCE

Lack of resources to solve problems, phone calls, meetings, lack of priorities, poor communication and company visits. Managers and employees fall into time traps for various reasons. The most important of these reasons are: indecision, interruptions, shifting priorities, lack of time for personal life and planning, and lack of prioritization. In organizations, situations such as insufficient workforce, inability to devote oneself to work, coming to work late, poor communication, multitasking, mistakes, demoralization and insufficient information are among the important time traps.

Phone Calls

In order to prevent the phone from becoming a time trap; unnecessary conversations should not be made on the phone, what is to be said should be clear in advance, the message should be conveyed clearly and it is necessary to be a good receiver.

Visitors

The fact that the meeting with the manager was not planned **and that the** questions to be asked and the answers to be given were not finalized in advance shows that unplanned visits are among the time traps.

Unnecessary Meetings

Meetings are one of the important responsibilities that every manager has to fulfill. Because meetings fulfill many functions such as the distribution of tasks, decision-making, and the emergence of creativity.

Working Environment

Factors such as the tidiness, noiselessness, lighting, furnishings and the design and location of the room have an impact on human productivity.

Time Traps from Management Approach

Refusal to Delegate Authority and Duties

The most important factor here is that the delegation of authority should be at a level that can contribute to the willingness to work and job satisfaction of subordinate managers and save time for the manager. " It is the transfer of certain powers and responsibilities from senior management to subordinate management." (Tutar, 2007; p. 112) One of the reasons why job transfer cannot be realized is that there is no one to delegate to. If a job needs to be done quickly and the manager does not have enough employees, it is a good reason not to delegate this job. Sometimes there are employees, but they may not have the knowledge and experience to do the task. For example, if the employee does not have enough time to learn how to do the task, it is a valid reason to delegate. Employees who lack knowledge and experience need time to acquire it.

Inadequate Communication

There are time traps in organizational life caused by inadequate communication. The vast majority of businesses spend time in written and verbal communication with other people. In this time, lack of communication is a major time-wasting factor. One of the causes of poor communication is interruptions. For example, when you are working on a report, one of your colleagues walks in and starts talking. One needs to turn one's attention away from the report and towards what one's friend is saying.

One of the pitfalls of time is difficulties with language and expression. Language is the main element of communication. If it is used in a complex way, it leads to communication difficulties. For this reason, a simple and descriptive language should be used in

communication. There is a language for using time. When we speak fast, we convey that we do not have much time. A good example is people who have a lot to say at meetings but no time.

Uncertainty of Managerial Objectives

In today's business world, the possibility of making mistakes is quite high when people need to prioritize in order to maintain a successful situation. "Managerial goals should be clearly and simply set out by the organization in order to be able to identify and determine the goals that employees will achieve." (Sabuncuoğlu-Paşa-Kaymaz, 2010; p.25-27) People who set their goals and objectives well are not affected by time traps and focus only on the work to be done.

Coordination

" Coordination is a function that brings together human efforts in order for a job to be done effectively and ensures that this cooperation is carried out with the most appropriate environment, time, personnel and materials." (Karaoğlu, 2006; p. 97) Coordination prevents complexity in organizations and creates positive results for both employees and the business. Thus, while motivating people, the business works more effectively. Coordination increases efficiency when it prevents reciprocity for the company.

Crises and Organizational

Crisis" is defined as threats that may affect the products, services, methods and processes of the business and its reputation or goodwill (Smither, Houston and Mdtire, 1996; p. 448). Rapid changes in the environment, uncertainty, inaccurate data, unhealthy communication, lack of coordination within and outside the organization are the most important causes of

CURRENT SCIENCE

crisis. In times of crisis, people spend most of their time solving new problems and are unable to think about their actual job description. Organizational crises should be planned in advance. A team should be formed and the measures to be taken should be determined in advance.

Age:

Gender:

Queue	Survey Question	Yes	Somet imes	No.
1	Do you plan before you start your work?			
2	Do you set a goal to get things done?			
3	Do deadlines cause you stress?			
4	Do you work overtime to get things done?			
5	Do you create a to-do list before you start work?			
6	Do you spend enough time on your personal development?			
7	Do you think the meetings are wasting your time?			

CURRENT SCIENCE

8	Do you think traffic takes up your time where you live?			
9	Do you think you spend too much time on social media during the day?			
10	Do you procrastinate often?			
11	Do you have time for socializing?			
12	Is your desk organized?			
13	Do you feel like you have done nothing at the end of the day?			
14	Do you ever miss deadlines because you can't say no to your colleagues?			
15	When there is more than one thing to do, do you find it difficult to prioritize them?			
16	Do you think you use your time efficiently?			
17	Do you allocate enough time for the things you are really good at?			

CURRENT SCIENCE

18	Are you achieving the goals you set during the day?			
19	Can you make quick decisions?			
20	Does stress negatively affect your time management?			

5. Conclusion

Using time efficiently and effectively is entirely in our hands. By controlling how we spend time, we can identify time traps and make time use more efficient. Most of the time we worry about the intensity of work, but the real cause of our anxiety is the inability to manage time well. Time management relieves anxiety, provides discipline, increases performance and productivity. Time management trainings contribute to people at this stage; topics such as planning, setting priorities, decision-making, stress management arising from time management are addressed. Thus, it provides a balance between work and life. As a result, time is a valuable concept. Every moment we do not live will not come again. We should live knowing this and appreciate it.

Bibliography:

- SABUNCUOĞLU Zeyyat - PAŞA Muammer - KAYMAZ Kurtuluş, Time Management, 2nd Edition, Beta Basım Yayın Dağıtım A.Ş., İstanbul 2010
- KOÇEL Tamer, Business Management, 11th Edition, Arıkan Basım Yayın Dağıtım, İstanbul 2007

- İŞCAN Ömer Faruk, Bilgi Toplumunda Zaman Yönetimi Ve Bankacılık Sektöründe Yöneticiler Üzerine Bir Uygulama, (Master's Thesis), Atatürk University Institute of Social Sciences, Department of Business Administration 1999
- EMMETT Rita, Manage Time to Reduce Your Stress, 1st Edition, Kariyer Publishing, Istanbul 2009
- KARAOĞLAN Aslan Deniz, Time Management of Top Level Managers, (Master's Thesis), Balıkesir University Institute of Science and Technology Department of Industrial Engineering, February 2006
- Elias, Norbert. (2000). On Time, (translated by V. Atayman). Istanbul: Ayrıntı Publications
- DOĞRUÖZ, İ. Planning Of Time Management On Goal Setting. An Application For Managers In Different Sectors. Istanbul: Marmara University, Institute of Social Sciences, Master's Thesis, 2008.
- Aslan Deniz Karaoğlan, Time Management of Top Level Managers, (Master's Thesis), Balıkesir University Institute of Science and Technology, Department of Industrial Engineering, February 2006, p.69
- Smither, Robert D" John M. Houston and Sandra A. Muntire (1996); Organization Development: Strategies for Changing Environments; HarperCollinsCollegePublishers, for USA.
- SMITH, Hyrum W.; 10 Natural Laws of Managing Life and Time: Proven Strategies for Increasing Productivity and Inner Peace, 1st Edition, (Translated by Adalet Çelbiş), Sistem Publishing, February 1998, Istanbul